

Project Title: Forgiveness and reconciliation rituals: Pathways to depolarization for adolescents in rural Kenya, Cameroon and Ethiopia

Sociodemographic, Focus Group Discussion guide and Individual interview guides and Psychometric Tests

Recruitment

500 adolescents between the ages of 10-18 years of age from Kenya, Ethiopia and Cameroon. Total 1500 youth-750 male. Half of all the participants (750) are in the control group. Interviews and discussions offer qualitative exploratory data. Extremism and prosocialism scales measure the efficacy of the intervention module offered.

Research Instruments

Sample: Kenya. English Turkana version

Socio-demographic survey instrument

Adapted from local countries (Kenya, Ethiopia, Cameroon) routine national demographic surveys. We will add items collecting adolescent social network information.

1. Name **Ekiro**
2. Residence Hut/stone house/urban/rural. **Aluwae erae awii**
3. Religion **Aluwae ilipia iyong**
4. Age **Ng'ikaur**
5. Gender Male Female **Ikile/Iberu**
6. Marital status Polygamous (number of wives/co-wives) Monogamous. **Iutarit iyong ng'aae**
7. Number of children (girls/boys). **Ng'ide ng'iaae**
8. Highest education level attained. **Esal akiswam kon**
9. Non-school going-How do you occupy yourself during the day in the community? **Ikonene iyong ibooe anakwariae?**
10. School-going-How do you occupy you when you are on school holidays? ? **Ikonene iyong ibooe ng'irwa luegolitere esukulae?**

11.

12. What type of people do you consider friends? **Ng'itunga nyo imina iyong erae ng'ipalon kon?**

13. What type of people do you not like very much? **Ng'itunga nyo nyimina iyong noe aloboyor kon**

Adolescent social networks

1. Who would you go to for help when you have a problem? Mention type of problem and person(s) helping adolescent

Aluwae ilosene iyong asait naiyakar iyong echanit?

Who do you typically spend your time with in sample 24 hour period. What do you do at this time?

Ngae imina arukit ka ng'esi anakwar. Inyo isubi yong ka ngesi ng'asain ng'una?

Weekday (choose a typical one) **toseu asait ng'ina**

Morning from waking up to mid-morning **Ataparach anyoun tanang aapiar lotingilan**

Afternoon to dusk **Ebong tanang niechea**

After dusk **akisiakin achaet**

Weekend (choose one day) **Akwaar Nakiyang'aret** (toseu akwaar apei)

Morning From waking up to mid-morning **Ataparach anyoun tanang aapiar lotingilan**

Afternoon to dusk **Ebong tanang niechea**

After dusk **akisiakin achaet**

Focus Group Discussion guide items (With groups of stakeholders)

1. Please describe some reasons why conflict erupts in the community. Who is involved, why are they involved, how are they involved?

Kisaisau tani ibore nieyauni ejie kori aremo anadakarini? Tang'ae eminentete, kotere nyo irepunere kechi toomi, ikwanakinio irepuni kechae?

2. Describe the process of resolving such conflict.

Kisisau ng'irotin lu etiekenere ng'ikesio lu ikote ng'ulu?

3. **Who is usually present at forgiveness and reconciliation ceremonies?** Ng'ae eminene nitekenere ng'ikesio lu arimanakin ka abong'okin?
4. **What rituals occur during a forgiveness and reconciliation ceremony? (at the beginning, middle, end)** ng'italio nyo eminenete ng'irwa lu arimanakin ka abong'okin
5. **What role do you play in these ceremonies?** Inyo etich kon ngirwa la ng'ikesio ka lu?
6. **What do you think is the benefit of these ceremonies? (To you? the community?)** Inyo ajekis akiwanakin ng'ikesio kama ta lu?
7. **What were your feelings towards your perceived enemy during and after the ceremony?** Inyo abu etau kon kitamak kidiami emoit kon adaunet eekes?
8. **Why do you think you felt this way? (During, after?)** inyo etilimuni etau kon ibore ng'ini?

Interviews with 4 participants nominated community focal persons knowledgeable in relevant rituals

1. Describe your day to day occupation
Kisisau tani inyo etich isubene yong
2. What is your position in the community?
Inyo napas kon alotomii adakar?
3. What type of conflict occur in a community?
Aina nyo eng'urng'ur iminene tomii adakar
4. What is the process of resolving these conflicts?
Isianakinio adaun eng'urng'ur lokoai?

5. **What rituals occur in forgiveness and reconciliation ceremonies?** ng'italio nyo eminenete ng'irwa lu arimanakin ka abong'okin
6. Who is present during these rituals? **Ng'ae eminene asait naesubene ng'italio luku?**
7. Describe the role these people present play in this ceremony **Inyo napas kori etich ang'itunga alumenenete asait na esubenere ng'italio kori akitiak ng'ikesio?**
8. **What role do you play in forgiveness and reconciliation ceremonies?** Inyo ekas/etich kon anakitiak ng'ikesio lu ariminakino ka ayaun ng'itung'a aapei??
9. **What do you think are the benefits of these rituals?** Inyo ing'olikinit Iyong Atamar erai ajekis ang'italio kaluu?

Extremism Scale developed by Ozer Simon & Bertelsen, Preben. (2018).

Items	S A	T A	N A	N	N D	T D	S D
<p>1. Most people lead a way of life and traditions that require change entirely</p> <p>Ng'itung'a lukaalak iwapito eboyor ka ng'italio lu echamakina ilokonyo.</p>							
<p>2. If one cannot conform to the majority's way of life and traditions, one requires to change to a very different way of life and tradition for oneself and one's companions</p> <p>Pe kepedo ipei akilokonyikin ka akiwapakin ngirotin alukalak lu akiyar ka ngitalio ka ngini pei ka ni erukitotor</p>							
<p>3. The productive system that is the foundation of society requires to be completely changed.</p>							

<p>Ngipitesio lu erekinitai lu erai asidir kop anadakar lu esakitai ilokonyo</p>							
<p>4. Like-minded people have to rigorously alter the bases of their own life in total. Others are free to do what they like.</p> <p>Ngitunga lu ikwaan Ngitamem kec itimokino ekenyikinete ngipitesio a eboyor kec lojojokon.Ngice esubete eger lo esakete keci</p>							
<p>5. It is essential to remove democratic types of government if we want to have an acceptable society.</p> <p>Kipedori alemar aring na eseunito ngitunga kisaki eboyor lo echamakina</p>							
<p>6. I do not care how the rest of the society chooses to be governed – Me, and those like me, will establish different governments at our own time.</p> <p>Nekacit ayong eger lo esaket luce kitorik,ayong ka luce lu kikwaan ka ayong kiwakini angolennyang nakosi analolom kosi</p>							
<p>7. Me, and those like me, actually do not share anything with the rest of the community.</p> <p>ayong ka luce lu kikwaan ka ayong nikimoren ka luce anadakar ibore</p>							

<p>8. There are no two ways to live the fine and exact life, only one.</p> <p>Keyei itwan nipenesaki akiboi alorot aloechamakina aloboyor, echamakina itwaan ng'ina echadario</p>							
<p>9. If someone does not live in accordance with the fine and exact life, then one has opted to isolate from society.</p> <p>Keyei itwan nipenesaki akiboi alorot aloechamakina aloboyor, echamakina itwaan ng'ina echadario.</p>							
<p>10. Those groupings in the community that don't agree to the fine and exact life should be denied certain rights</p> <p>Ng'alogitae ng'una alore nape nesakete akiwap erot lokajokon aloboyor echamakina imikio aten kech</p>							
<p>11. It is futile to try to discover answers with those who think about life entirely differently from us.</p>							
<p>12. It is not right to engage in arguments over what one believes in.</p> <p>Niechamakina ilomari loburas kotere ng'akiro nienupit itwaan.</p>							

<p>13. It is not acceptable to live in peace with people who do not live the fine and exact life.</p> <p>Niechamakina esilio ka ng'itung'a lupenesakete akiboi eboyor lo asegan na loo echamakina.</p>							
<p>14. Finally, there must be a clash– one cannot continuously live-in harmony with people who live an entirely contrasting life from the one they are supposed to live</p> <p>Arumori, eyei akigumguma eboyer alikolong' eboiyete ng'itung'a ka eboyer lo itatamio ng'itung'a kiboyokinos.</p>							

Prosocialness scale for adults. Caprara et al 2006a

The following statements describe a large number of common situations. There are no right or wrong answers; the best answer is the immediate, spontaneous one. Read each phrase carefully and fill in the number that reflects your first reaction.

Elimorito ng'akiran nuku kidiama ng'akuro nakalak naesubanasi. Eman alimoret na ateni kori na alioko. Alimoret daang ng'esi na esaa kaloo. Kiswamau daang loge nakaneni kileleb tomii anamba na ing'olikinit yong atamar itiemokino ka atamet kon.

1	2	3	4	5
Never/Almost Never	Rarely	Occasionally	Often	Always/Almost
Always				

1. I am pleased to help my friends/colleagues in their activities. **1 2 3 4 5**

Ayakanar ayong etau la aking'arakin ng'ipalon kang akisub kitichisio kech

2. I share the things that I have with my friends. 1 2 3 4 5

Kitekene ayong ka ng'ipalon kang ibore ni ayakar ayong?

3. I try to help others. 1 2 3 4 5

Eng'aranakini ayong ng'itung'a luche

4. I am available for volunteer activities to help those who are in need. 1 2 3 4
5

Alemuna ayong pas alotichisio aking'arakin ng'itung'a lu esakete aking'arakino

5. I am empathic with those who are in need. 1 2 3 4 5

Ayakanar ayong ng'isen kidiana ng'itunga lu esakete ang'arasit

6. I immediately help those who are in need. 1 2 3 4 5

Eng'aranakini atipei ng'itung'a lu esakenete ang'arasit

7. I do what I can to help others avoid getting into trouble. 1 2 3 4
5

Esubene ayong ibore daang' aking'arakin ng'itung'a luche tojong'oto alomanar lochan

8. I intensely feel what others feel 1 2 3 4 5

Eger lo eminene etau lokang ng'esi bile lominenete lukech dae

9. I am willing to make my knowledge and abilities available to others 1 2 3 4
5

Alemuna ayong akitumiar ng'atameta ka niapedori ayong alotung'a aluche

10. I try to console those who are sad 1 2 3 4 5

Ening'onokini ayong aking'it ka aking'arakin lu itasiononosi

11. I easily lend money or other things 1 2 3 4 5

Edenonori ayong ng'aropiae ka ng'iborei luche

12. I easily put myself in the shoes of those who are in discomfort 1 2 3 4 5

Alomanari ayong atipei tomii ng'amuk ang'itunga aluemakatar ibore kori aluesakete ang'arasit

13. I try to be close to and take care of those who are in need 1 2 3 4
5

Aminene ayong edie ka aking'arakin ng'itung'a lu esakete ang'arasit

14. I easily share with friends any good opportunity that comes to me 1 2 3 4
5

Kimorene ayong ka ng'ipalon ibore daang niajokon niebunene nikang

15. I spend time with those friends who feel lonely 1 2 3 4 5

Alemanari ayong asait nakang akiruk ka ng'ipalon kang lu itetee atamar kiya make/kori lu esilikinit

16. I immediately sense my friends' discomfort even when it is not directly communicated to me. 1 2 3 4 5

Ayenene ayong ng'ipaalon kang lu emanatar ibore kori lu eyakanatar ng'ichan teni asait nape nelimuntotor kech